

**ECONOMIC AND CULTURAL TRADE ROUTES OF THE PEOPLES OF
CENTRAL ASIA IN ANCIENT TIMES****Zebinisobegim Begnazarova**

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Abstract: In this article, the results of various studies about the economic and cultural trade routes of the Middle Ossetian peoples in ancient times are given in detail.

Key words: Central Asia, Egypt, India, silk, silk, rice

During the Eneolithic and Bronze Age, a number of historical processes took place that accelerated the development of Ancient Eastern civilization (Mesopotamia, Old Asia, Egypt, Elam, Indus Valley, Central Asia, etc.). Among them, metallurgy, irrigated agriculture, the emergence of city-states and large state associations, water transport, and the beginning of the use of land-based drafts (horses, camels, donkeys, etc.) and vehicles (carts of various shapes and sizes) such important discoveries were of great importance. From this period, the formation of the system of communication and trade routes connecting Central Asia with the Ancient Eastern world laid the foundation for the integration of our region into the emerging system of international economic and cultural relations. This period is of great importance as the period in which continuous communication with the centers of Ancient EAST civilizations of our region was established for the first time. In the Eneolithic and Bronze Age, economic motives played an important role in the formation of large transit communication routes connecting Central Asia with the first centers of the Ancient Eastern civilization. In particular, in the countries of the Ancient East, there was a great demand for metal and non-metallic products, precious stones and rare minerals brought from the southern countries of our region, primarily from Sugdiyana and Bactria. Among such products, Badakhshan lojvardi, which was highly valued in the Ancient East, was especially important (Dandamaev M.A., Lukonin V.G., 1980, p. 117). "Lojuvard Road", which has an important place in the foreign relations of our region and is considered to be the oldest among the transit communication routes, started from the Lojuvard mines in Badakhshan Mountain and reached the territory of Mesopotamia and Egypt. This is evidenced by various objects made of louvard found as a result of historical and archaeological research in Sumer and Akkad and Egyptian cities (Kultura i iskusstvo Vavilonii, Assirii i sosednih stran, 1953, p. 8; CHAyld G.,

1956, p. 202). Badakhshan Lojuvardi went to India during the considered period (Sagdullaev A.S., 2000, p. 119), mil. avv. It is known that it was delivered to China from the middle of the 1st millennium (Mavlonov O.M., Mahkamova D., 2003, pp. 64-68; Kobzeva O.P., 2005, p. 6). The road that started from the Lojuvard mines in Badakhshan passed through Shortokai area⁴¹, located on the left bank of the Amudarya, north of the confluence of the Kokcha river with the Amudarya. Here the road branched and one direction led to Northern India through the valley of the Kabul River and the mountain passes of the Indian Kush. The Shortokai monument served as the main intermediate point for the delivery of Badakhshan iron and steel and non-metallic raw materials from the central regions of Central Asia to India. Among the various finds found in Shortokai, various jewelry made of Badakhshan lapis lazuli were found. This monument, built by representatives of the Harappan culture in Northern India, is an important link in the relations of the Harappans with the Central Asian region, in particular, in the delivery of the products of the lapis lazuli mines in Badakhshan to Northern India. This monument was discovered by French archaeologists in 1975-76 in Northern Afghanistan, at the confluence of the Kokcha River with the Amudarya. From this monument, which consists of 6 separate mounds (two of which have been archaeologically investigated), there are also products made from the Badakhshan Lojuvardi. (See: Frankfort H.P., 1982. p. 30-32). shows that it has fulfilled the function of a point (Sagdullaev A.S., 2000, p. 119). Mile through Shortokai. avv. The fact that economic and cultural relations between India and different regions of Central Asia were established in the 3rd millennium confirms that it was formed in connection with the activity of important transit routes. The route of the Lojuvard road from Shortokai to Mesopotamia passed through the Mundigak monuments found near Kandahar in present-day Afghanistan and Shahri-Sukhta monuments in Seyistan, Iran. Experts note that this transit communication and trade route played an important role in the formation of the city of Mundigak, which is an important intermediate point of the Lojuvard road. The next important intermediate point of the Lojuvard road is the Shahri Sokhta monument, the center of the first agricultural culture in the Seyistan oasis⁴². The fact that this monument is located at the crossroads of important communication routes of the Bronze Age is also shown by its connections with proto-cities in Southern Turkmenistan. This ancient city, which played an important role in the export of Badakhshan lojuvard to Iran and Mesopotamia, was also a large craft center where various jewelry and other products were made from lojuvard (History of

Drevnogo Vostoka, 1988, p. 251). Further routes of the Lojuvard road passed through the city-states of Mesopotamia. From the ruins of the city of Uruk, one of the ancient cities of Mesopotamia (Kultura i iskusstvo Vavilonii, Assirii i sosednih stran, 1953, p. 8), and from the "Tomb of the King" in the city of Ur, located in Southern Iraq in 1922-1934, by the English archaeologist Leonard Woolley, from the Badakhshan Lojuvardi various items made were found. Sumerian pottery also features gold, silver and lapis lazuli from the remote mountainous region. There is information about the bride. These findings, along with clarifying the directions of the Lojuvard road, show that Lojuvard was used in ancient times for making various jewelry and decorating the palace of rulers. In the ruins of the famous city of Troy located in Asia Minor (Hissarlik tepa)⁴³ products made of Badakhshan lapis lazuli were found. avv. Evidence that in the 2nd millennium, it entered Asia Minor from the upper reaches of Amudarya through the territory of Iran. Mil. avv. As early as the second half of the 4th century, many products - tin, silver, Mesopotamian seals, etc. - were brought from Asia to Egypt through mutual exchange. Among these findings, it is noteworthy that there are jewelry made from Badakhshan lojuvard, the oldest of which belong to the period when the centralized state was not yet established in the Nile Valley. allows us to determine the beginning of the period with the end of the Neolithic period - the beginning of the Eneolithic period. Thus, in the countries of the Ancient East, there is a need for Badakhshan lojuvard. avv. In the IV-III millennia, it started from the louvard deposits in the mountainous Badakhshan region located in the upper reaches of the Amudarya, and extended to various regions of Central Asia, as well as to India, Iran, Mesopotamia, Ancient Asia and Egypt, and was an important place in international relations. led to the formation of the "Great Lojuvard Road". This communication-trade route has a wide network. avv. During the IV-II millennia This monument was first discovered and studied by the famous German archeologist Heinrich Schliemann in the 19th century. It has gained great importance as a major transit communication route of the ancient Eastern world. The need for this rare mineral remained at a high level even in later periods. This is confirmed by information in medieval written sources (Marco Polo, 2005, p. 77; Makhmud ibn Vali, 1977, p. 23, 39, 47; Popov A.N., 1853, p. 272; Akhmedov B., 1985, p. .214) and also confirms that since the 19th century, the Afghan government has strictly controlled the use of coal mines (Babakhodjaev M.A., 1975, p. 63). In the relations of Central Asia with the centers of the ancient civilization of the East, not only the trade of goods occupied a large place, but these relations covered all

spheres of economic and cultural life. The region's relations with India, Iran, Mesopotamia and other countries date back thousands of years. avv. It became more active in IV-III millennia. This can also be seen in the example of similarities in the construction of temples and other structures, pottery and figurines (Masson V.M., 1981v, p. 104-112; 2000, p. 114-117; Isakov A.I., 1986, p. 116; 1991 , p. 57; Eshov B.J., 2004; 2006; Archeology zarubezhnoy Azii., 1986, p. 120-121). Such closeness in material culture, of course, indicates the activity of economic and cultural relations carried out along the relevant communication routes.. In particular, in the Eneolithic and Bronze Age, a system of communication routes connecting the southern and central regions of Marquesas Asia with Iran and Mesopotamia was formed. The main direction of these communication routes passed through monuments such as Anov, Nomozgoh and Altintepa in Southern Turkmenistan, Zamonbabo and Sarazm in the Zarafshan oasis, and led to the inner regions of Central Asia. According to our opinion, the communication route leading from Mesopotamia to the upper reaches of the Zarafshan River was in the direction of Nomozgoh - Murgob oasis - Zamonbobob - Sarazm. In the foreign economic and cultural relations of Central Asia during this period, Northern India also played a major role. Mil. avv. Permanent contacts were established between the Harappan and Mahenjo-Daro cultures, which appeared in the Indus River valley in the III millennium and played an important role in the development of the ancient Eastern civilization, and the Bronze Age cultures of Central Asia, and qualitatively reached a new stage. rose. It is known that India's relations with Mesopotamia began in the Eneolithic period and were carried out through the Indian Ocean and the Persian Gulf, i.e. waterways (Rtveladze E.V., 1999, pp. 16-17). India's relations with our region were mainly carried out by land routes, that is, through the Indian Kush mountain passes. The consistent use of Hindukush mountain passes began in the Neolithic period, and mountain roads in several directions were developed over time. These routes are divided into northern and southern parts, the northern route connecting India with present-day Kabul and the surrounding areas and the upper reaches of the Ox (Amu Darya) River, northern Iran and southern Central Asia, and the southern route and connected the lower reaches of the Indus River (Mahenjo-Daro) and Northern Baluchistan (a province in present-day Pakistan) with the central and southern regions of Iran through Mundigak (Willer M., 2005, pp. 11-12, 99, Ris. 19; SHirinov T.SH., 1990, p. 43). The economic and cultural connections of the civilization centers of the Indus River Valley with the proto-urban cultures of the south of Central Asia

(Altintepa, Nomozgoh) are also visible in the material finds. Other material finds include similar ceramic figurines found in the settlements belonging to the Harappan culture in southern Turkmenistan and India, the presence of ivory objects in different cultural layers of Altintep, and the influence of the Harappan and Mohenjo-Daro cultures in some ceramic and metal objects (Masson V.M., 1986, p. 13; Shetenko A.YA., 1974, p. 38-43) is the result of intense economic and cultural relations of these regions.

The ancient Turks called this river Ukuz. This term may have been called Ox by the Greeks in accordance with their pronunciation. (See: Mahmud Kashgari, 1960, pp. 91, 411; Kamoliddin SH.S., 2006a, p. 26).

Mil. avv. From the 2nd millennium, the roads connecting India with places in the Murgob oasis began to form. This communication route was in two directions: 1) Harappa-Kvett-Mundigak-Altintepa-Murgob oasis pottery complex; 2) Harappa - Shortokai - Dashli - Murgob oasis. The activity of this communication route can be seen in the similarity of some finds and architectural structures in the Murgab oasis and in India (Shetenko A.YA., 1970, pp. 23-24). Another important route of India's relations with our region led to the inner regions of the region, passing through the Bronze Age sites of Northern Afghanistan and the Surkhan oasis (Dashli, Sopolli, Jarquton). A mile along the road in this direction. avv. Economic and cultural cooperation in the 2nd millennium is confirmed by material findings, in particular, stone and metal eagle seals found at the Sopollitepa monument (SHirinov T.SH., 2000, p. 118).

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